

Translation Style in the *Diamond Sutra*: An Interpretable Stylometric Comparison of Kumārajīva and Xuanzang

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Abstract. The present study applies character-frequency stylometry and principal component analysis (PCA) to a comparison of the Kumārajīva and Xuanzang translations of the *Diamond Sutra* (*Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra*). Using overlapping fixed-length textual segments drawn from digitized CBETA editions, the study examines whether statistically detectable stylistic distinctions can be identified between two parallel translations of the same Buddhist scripture. The analysis shows that the two translations form distinguishable, though partially overlapping, clusters in PCA space despite their broadly similar doctrinal content. Principal component loadings reveal that Kumārajīva's translation is more strongly associated with canonical dialogue markers and formulaic scriptural discourse, whereas Xuanzang's translation exhibits a greater concentration of connective narration, expository prose structure, and technically precise Buddhist terminology, including a stronger retention of transliterated Indic expressions. Shannon entropy analysis confirms that the two translations are broadly comparable in overall lexical diversity, indicating that the stylistic separation identified by PCA reflects differences in discourse organization and terminological distribution rather than global differences in textual complexity. The findings suggest, within this limited parallel corpus, interpretable stylometric analysis can indicate translator-associated differences that merit further philological comparison.

Keywords: Stylometry, Principal Component Analysis, Digital Humanities, Chinese Buddhist Translation, *Diamond Sutra*, Computational Philology.

1 Introduction

Stylometry has provided a productive quantitative approach to questions of textual style, authorship, and attribution. While early landmark studies such as Mosteller and Wallace's (1964) analysis of *The Federalist Papers* demonstrated that word-frequency distributions could resolve questions of disputed authorship, subsequent research has extended stylometric methods to a wider range of linguistic and textual variation (Burrows, 1992; Hoover, 2003; Stamatatos, 2009). Applying such methods to classical Chinese, however, requires methodological adjustment: the absence of word boundaries and the instability of segmentation standards in pre-modern Chinese make word-level analysis unreliable. Character-level representation offers a more robust alternative, since individual written characters in classical Chinese simultaneously carry graphemic, morphemic, and semantic functions. Bingenheimer, Hung, and Hsieh (2017) demonstrated the viability of this approach by applying principal component analysis to grammatical particle frequencies in Chinese translations of the *Gaṇḍavyūha*, identifying historically meaningful stylistic patterns across translation periods. The present study builds on this foundation by expanding the feature set beyond particles to the 300 most frequent characters across the corpus, and by shifting from diachronic comparison to a translator-oriented parallel design.

The *Diamond Sutra* (*Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra*) offers a well-suited test case because multiple Chinese translations of the same scripture survive, allowing topical

variation to be minimized while translational choices remain available for comparison. This study focuses on the translations attributed to Kumārajīva (ca. 401 CE) and Xuanzang (ca. 648 CE), two of the most influential figures in Chinese Buddhist translation history. Kumārajīva's translations are widely characterized as fluent and naturalized into Chinese literary idiom, whereas Xuanzang's are noted for terminological precision and systematic retention of Indic linguistic structures (Zürcher, 2007). Both translators operated within large-scale institutional frameworks, and their work reflects not only individual style but also the evolving conventions of collaborative translation teams (Siu, 2024). The present analysis therefore treats stylistic patterns as properties of translation traditions rather than of individual authorial voice alone.

Against this background, this study asks two related questions: first, whether statistically detectable stylistic differences exist between the two translations at the character-frequency level; and second, whether the nature of those differences, as identified by principal component analysis, corresponds to philologically recognized contrasts in Buddhist translation style. Rather than restricting the feature set to grammatical particles, the analysis examines the 300 most frequent characters across fixed-length textual segments, allowing both function-like markers and semantically charged Buddhist terminology to contribute to the stylistic representation.

The contribution of this paper is threefold. First, it extends prior Buddhist stylometric work by applying a multi-featured character-frequency approach to parallel translations of the same scripture, moving beyond the grammatical-particle restriction of earlier studies. Second, it offers quantitative patterns that are broadly consistent with prior philological characterizations of Kumārajīva's and Xuanzang's translation styles. Third, and more broadly, it argues for positioning interpretable stylometry as a form of computational philology in which statistical patterns and philological judgment function as complementary rather than competing modes of textual evidence.

2 Methodology

The study combines stylometric feature extraction with exploratory statistical analysis in order to examine stylistic variation between the two Chinese translations of the *Diamond Sutra*. The methodological workflow consists of five stages: corpus preparation, text preprocessing, overlapping text segmentation, character-frequency representation, and dimensionality reduction through principal component analysis (PCA). In addition, Shannon entropy was calculated to provide a complementary measure of lexical diversity across textual segments.

Rather than treating stylometry as a classification task aimed primarily at predictive accuracy, the present study adopts an interpretive approach that emphasizes the philological readability of statistical patterns. Accordingly, the analysis focuses not only on cluster separation in PCA space, but also on the interpretability of principal component loadings and their relationship to historically recognized translation styles.

2.1 Corpus

This study examines two Chinese translations of the *Diamond Sutra* (*Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra*): the translation attributed to Kumārajīva and the later translation attributed to Xuanzang. Digital texts were obtained from the Chinese Buddhist Electronic Text Association (CBETA), which provides standardized electronic editions of the Chinese Buddhist canon.

To improve comparability between the two translations, editorial punctuation, editorial symbols, and non-Chinese characters were removed during preprocessing. Because punctuation in modern CBETA editions reflects contemporary editorial decisions rather than original manuscript features, the primary analysis was conducted on punctuation-removed texts. Character normalization was otherwise kept minimal in order to preserve lexical and stylistic differences between the two translations.

After preprocessing, the Kumārajīva translation contained approximately 5,174 Chinese characters, whereas the Xuanzang translation contained approximately 8,225 characters. Since the two texts differ substantially in total length, the analysis was performed on fixed-length textual segments rather than on entire texts as single units.

2.2 Text preprocessing

Whitespace, Arabic numerals, Latin characters, and editorial formatting symbols were removed from the source texts prior to analysis. The primary experiment retained only Chinese characters within the Unicode CJK range. Punctuation was excluded because modern punctuation in CBETA editions represents later editorial intervention rather than features of the historical translations themselves.

No word segmentation was performed. Since segmentation standards for classical and Buddhist Chinese remain methodologically unstable, the study adopted a character-level representation following earlier work in Chinese Buddhist stylometry (Bingenheimer et al., 2017). Character-level representation is particularly suitable for classical Chinese Buddhist texts, where individual written characters often carry grammatical, semantic, and terminological functions simultaneously. In this context, character frequencies should not be understood merely as orthographic counts, but rather as distributional traces of Buddhist discourse, formulaic expression, and translation choices.

The preprocessing procedure was intentionally conservative. Apart from removing editorial symbols and non-Chinese characters, no additional normalization or lemmatization was applied. This design aimed to preserve stylistically meaningful lexical variation between the two translations.

2.3 Text segmentation

To obtain multiple comparable observational units from each translation, the texts were divided into overlapping fixed-length segments. Each segment consisted of 800 Chinese characters, with a stride length of 400 characters between consecutive segments.

The segmentation procedure should not be understood as sentence-level or passage-level semantic alignment. Rather, the study treats the two texts as parallel translations of the same

scripture and compares local character-frequency distributions across fixed-length windows. This design does not assume one-to-one correspondence between individual segments, but instead uses the shared doctrinal and narrative framework of the *Diamond Sutra* to reduce topical variation at the corpus level. The overlapping-window design produced partially shared textual contexts while reducing the instability that may arise from arbitrary segmentation boundaries.

The use of overlapping segments serves two purposes. First, it increases the number of observations available for exploratory statistical analysis. Second, it reduces the influence of sentence interruption caused by strict non-overlapping segmentation. Because classical Chinese Buddhist texts often contain long syntactic structures without clear sentence boundaries, overlapping windows provide a more stable approximation of local stylistic distributions. The overlapping design was therefore adopted primarily to stabilize local frequency distributions within long and weakly punctuated classical Chinese passages, rather than to inflate the number of statistically independent observations.

Using this procedure, the Kumārajīva translation yielded 11 textual segments, whereas the Xuanzang translation yielded 19 segments.

2.4 Character-frequency representation

Each textual segment was represented as a character-frequency vector. The analysis focused on the 300 most frequent Chinese characters across the combined corpus. The threshold of 300 characters was selected to balance feature coverage against the risk of including low-frequency noise. Given the limited size of the corpus, this threshold was intended to capture recurring stylistic and terminological patterns without allowing rare characters to dominate the analysis. This range is broadly consistent with feature set sizes employed in comparable character-level stylometric studies, and was judged sufficient to capture both functional and terminologically significant characters within the combined corpus. For each segment, the relative frequencies of these characters were calculated to produce a high-dimensional stylometric representation.

Unlike studies restricted to grammatical particles alone, the present approach allows both function-like markers and semantically meaningful Buddhist terminology to contribute to the feature space. As a result, the representation captures not only syntactic tendencies but also formulaic expressions, transliterated elements, doctrinal vocabulary, and recurring discourse structures.

Relative frequency normalization was used in order to reduce the influence of segment-length variation. The resulting matrix therefore represents stylistic distributional patterns rather than absolute character counts.

2.5 Principal component analysis

PCA was applied to the character-frequency matrix in order to identify the dominant axes of stylistic variation among textual segments. PCA transforms a high-dimensional feature space into a smaller number of orthogonal components while preserving as much variance as possible (Jolliffe, 2002).

Prior to PCA, the character-frequency matrix was standardized using z-score normalization in order to reduce the influence of scale differences among features.

In the present study, the first two principal components were used for visualization and interpretation. Scatter plots were employed to examine whether segments from the two translations formed distinguishable stylistic clusters. More importantly, the loadings of individual characters on each principal component were analyzed in order to identify which linguistic features contributed most strongly to stylistic separation.

Rather than treating PCA solely as a clustering tool, the study interprets principal component loadings as potentially meaningful philological evidence. Characters with high positive or negative loadings were therefore examined in relation to known differences in Buddhist translation style, including formulaic discourse markers, transliterated terminology, and naturalized Chinese syntactic patterns.

2.6 Shannon entropy

In addition to PCA, Shannon entropy was calculated for each textual segment as a complementary measure of lexical diversity. Shannon entropy estimates the degree of distributional unpredictability within a textual unit and has frequently been used in information theory and quantitative text analysis (Cover & Thomas, 2006).

For each segment, entropy was calculated based on character-frequency distributions. Higher entropy values indicate greater diversity and dispersion of character usage, whereas lower entropy values indicate greater concentration around a smaller set of frequently repeated characters.

The entropy analysis was not intended as an independent authorship measure, but rather as a supplementary descriptive statistic for comparing the overall lexical tendencies of the two translations. Boxplots were used to visualize the distribution of entropy values across textual segments.

To assess whether entropy differences between the two translations were statistically significant, both the Mann–Whitney U test and Welch’s t-test were performed.

3 Results

The results are presented in four stages. First, PCA visualization is used to examine whether the textual segments from the two translations form distinguishable stylistic clusters. The subsequent sections then analyze the character loadings associated with the first principal component (PC1) and the second principal component (PC2) in order to identify the linguistic features contributing to stylistic separation. Finally, Shannon entropy is examined as a supplementary measure of lexical diversity across the two translations.

3.1 PCA visualization

Principal component analysis revealed a visible and interpretable stylistic separation between the Kumārajīva and Xuanzang translations of the *Diamond Sutra*. When the textual segments were projected onto the first two principal components, the two translations formed distinguishable clusters in PCA space, although a limited degree of overlap remained.

Figure 1: PCA scatter plot of textual segments

PC1 explained 13.8% of the total variance, whereas PC2 explained 12.2%. This relatively modest level of explained variance is not unexpected in high-dimensional stylometric analysis, where stylistic signals are often distributed across many correlated textual features rather than concentrated in one or two dominant variables. Although the variance explained by each individual component was modest, the combined projection nevertheless produced a visually interpretable distinction between the two translations. Segments associated with Xuanzang tended to cluster toward the positive region of PC2 and the negative region of PC1, while Kumārajīva segments appeared more concentrated in the negative region of PC2 and the positive region of PC1. This directional separation provides the interpretive basis for the loading analyses presented in the following sections.

Importantly, the separation was not perfectly discrete. Rather than indicating methodological weakness, the partial overlap likely reflects the fact that both texts are translations of the same Buddhist scripture and therefore share substantial doctrinal and narrative structure. At the same time, the persistence of visible clustering suggests that differences in translation style remain detectable despite substantial doctrinal and narrative overlap.

The PCA results indicate that character-frequency distributions capture stylistic differences that are visible within this controlled parallel corpus. Given the shared doctrinal frame of the two texts, these differences are plausibly related to translational style rather than to broad topical divergence alone.

3.2 PC1 loadings

PC1 was associated with a contrast between two different modes of scriptural discourse organization. Characters with high positive loadings included 「云」、「何」、「佛」、「世」、「尊」、「言」, whereas characters with high negative loadings included 「事」、「復」、「當」、「乘」、「聽」、「稱」.

Character	Loading	Interpretation
云	0.126	canonical dialogue marker
何	0.125	interrogative scriptural formula
佛	0.115	Buddhist canonical discourse
名	0.115	doctrinal designation / naming
世	0.110	formulaic reference to the Buddha
尊	0.109	honorific canonical expression
言	0.099	formal speech marker
七	0.097	formulaic numerical expression
寶	0.097	doctrinal / merit-related terminology
滿	0.094	completeness / fulfillment expression
議	-0.098	discursive exposition
悉	-0.098	explanatory completeness marker
時	-0.100	narrative temporal transition
稱	-0.102	descriptive or referential usage
利	-0.102	practical / relational terminology
聽	-0.103	dialogic interaction
乘	-0.104	doctrinal narrative context
當	-0.105	explanatory modal structure
復	-0.108	connective narrative progression
事	-0.116	narrative or explanatory discourse

Table 1: Top positive and negative PC1 loadings

The positively weighted characters on PC1, including canonical dialogue markers such as 「佛言」 and interrogative formulas such as 「云何」, show higher relative frequencies in

the Kumārajīva translation when raw character counts are examined directly. This distributional pattern is consistent with the clustering of Kumārajīva segments toward the positive region of PC1 (Figure 1). By contrast, negatively weighted characters such as 「復」、「事」、「當」 are more closely associated with connective narration and explanatory prose flow, and appear more prominently in the Xuanzang translation.

Figure 2: Bar plot of top PC1 loadings

From a philological perspective, the PC1 axis may therefore be interpreted as reflecting a contrast between more formalized canonical discourse structure and more naturalized Chinese narrative flow. PC1 appears to index a contrast between more formulaic canonical dialogue markers and more connective expository narration in this corpus. In this sample, Kumārajīva segments are associated more strongly with the former, while Xuanzang segments are associated more strongly with the latter.

Importantly, this interpretation does not imply an absolute binary distinction. Rather, the principal component identifies the dominant statistical tendency that most strongly differentiates the two translations within the present corpus.

3.3 PC2 loadings

PC2 revealed a different stylistic contrast. Characters with high positive loadings included 「伽」、「由」、「因」、「緣」、「逝」、「現」, whereas highly negative loadings included 「菩」、「提」、「須」、「眾」、「人」.

Character	Loading	Interpretation
伽	0.153	transliterated Buddhist terminology
由	0.132	formal doctrinal connective
善	0.125	ethical / doctrinal vocabulary
殞	0.123	transliterated or technical term
緣	0.122	Buddhist causal terminology
因	0.122	Buddhist causal terminology
假	0.120	formal conditional expression
使	0.120	formal syntactic connector
逝	0.118	canonical epithet terminology
開	0.113	doctrinal exposition marker
耨	-0.093	transliterated Buddhist terminology
藐	-0.093	transliterated Buddhist terminology
即	-0.096	connective or identificatory marker
人	-0.098	human / personal reference
修	-0.098	practice-related terminology
萬	-0.105	numerical or hyperbolic expression
眾	-0.117	collective audience reference
須	-0.123	dialogic / personal reference
提	-0.128	established Chinese Buddhist terminology
菩	-0.141	established Chinese Buddhist terminology

Table 2: Top positive and negative PC2 loadings

Several positively weighted characters are associated with transliterated expressions, doctrinal terminology, or technical Buddhist vocabulary. Particularly notable is the character

「伽」, which in the present corpus appears predominantly within transliterated Sanskrit-derived compounds such as 「菟伽」 (Gaṅgā) and 「伽陀」, rather than in more naturalized Buddhist vocabulary. When considered alongside other positively weighted characters on PC2, including 「菟」 and doctrinal connectives such as 「因」 and 「緣」, the concentration of such features suggests a tendency toward greater terminological specificity and closer retention of Indic linguistic structure. These characteristics are compatible with an interpretation of Xuanzang's translation in this corpus as preserving more transliterated or technically specific terminology.

By contrast, negatively weighted characters such as 「須」、「眾」、「人」 are more closely associated with interpersonal dialogue and naturalized Chinese Buddhist discourse. These features appeared more prominently in the Kumārajīva translation. The resulting contrast may therefore be interpreted as a stylistic axis between technical or transliterative discourse and more idiomatic Chinese religious narration.

Figure 3: Bar plot of top PC2 loadings

Compared with PC1, which primarily reflects differences in discourse organization and formulaic structure, PC2 appears to capture variation related to doctrinal terminology and the balance between transliteration and naturalization. The coexistence of these two axes suggests that the stylistic distinction between the two translators cannot be reduced to a single dimension.

3.4 Entropy comparison

Shannon entropy analysis revealed only modest differences in lexical diversity between the two translations. The mean entropy value for the Kumārajīva segments was 6.665, whereas the Xuanzang segments showed a slightly higher mean value of 6.765.

Translator	Count	Mean Entropy	Std Dev	Min	25%	Median	75%	Max
Kumārajīva	11	6.665	0.264	6.157	6.525	6.648	6.846	7.033
Xuanzang	19	6.765	0.276	6.264	6.644	6.775	6.966	7.209

Table 3: Entropy summary statistics

Figure 4: Entropy boxplot

Although Xuanzang’s translation exhibited marginally greater entropy, the statistical tests did not indicate a significant difference between the two groups. The Mann-Whitney U test yielded $p=0.366$, while Welch’s t-test yielded $p=0.340$.

These results suggest that the two translations possess broadly comparable levels of lexical diversity despite their stylistic differences. The entropy results are consistent with the view that the PCA separation is not driven mainly by large differences in overall lexical diversity.

From a methodological perspective, the entropy results are important precisely because they do not show extreme divergence. If the two translations had exhibited dramatically different entropy values, the PCA separation might simply reflect large-scale differences in lexical richness. Instead, the modest entropy contrast suggests that the PCA separation is not driven mainly by broad differences in overall lexical diversity. Entropy is therefore used here as a diagnostic measure rather than a primary indicator of translation style.

It may appear counterintuitive that Xuanzang's translation, which exhibits more technically precise Buddhist terminology, should show marginally higher rather than lower entropy. This pattern is likely explained by the greater overall length and lexical variety of Xuanzang's text, which introduces a wider range of connective and expository vocabulary alongside its specialized terminology, thereby offsetting the concentrating effect of repeated technical terms. The entropy difference remains statistically non-significant and does not alter the primary interpretation.

Taken together, the PCA and entropy analyses indicate that statistically detectable stylistic distinctions exist between the Kumārajīva and Xuanzang translations, while also confirming that these differences remain embedded within a broadly shared doctrinal and textual framework.

4 Discussion

The results suggest that statistically detectable stylistic distinctions exist between the Kumārajīva and Xuanzang translations of the *Diamond Sutra*, even when the comparison is restricted to parallel translations of the same Buddhist scripture. Because the two texts share highly similar doctrinal content and narrative structure, the observed PCA separation is unlikely to reflect thematic variation alone. The controlled nature of the parallel corpus therefore helps reduce topical variation and allows stylistic distributions to emerge more clearly at the character-frequency level. The separation is consistent with differences in translational style, discourse organization, and terminological preference within this corpus.

An important finding is that the principal component loadings are philologically interpretable within this corpus. The positive side of PC1 is associated with characters such as 「云」、 「何」、 「佛」、 「世」、 「尊」, which frequently occur in formulaic Buddhist dialogue structures including 「佛言」 and 「云何」. Since Kumārajīva segments cluster toward the positive region of PC1, these features appear more characteristic of the Kumārajīva translation in this sample. By contrast, the negative side of PC1, toward which Xuanzang segments tend to cluster, contained characters such as 「復」、 「事」、 「當」, which are more closely associated with connective narration and explanatory prose flow. This contrast is broadly consistent with prior scholarly descriptions of Kumārajīva's translations as relatively fluent and naturalized into Chinese literary discourse, and Xuanzang's translations as comparatively more expository and systematically organized.

The PC2 results suggest a second stylistic dimension related to technical terminology and transliterated Buddhist expressions. Characters such as 「伽」, 「因」, 「緣」, and 「逝」 are associated with the positive side of the component, whereas characters such as 「菩」, 「提」, and 「眾」 are associated with the negative side. Particularly notable is the prominence of 「伽」, which frequently appears in transliterated Sanskrit-derived expressions. These features are compatible with an interpretation in which, in this corpus, Xuanzang's translation preserves more transliterated or technically specific terminology than Kumārajīva's.

Importantly, the present study does not claim that PCA directly “proves” historical interpretations of Buddhist translation style. Rather, the results demonstrate that quantitative character-frequency distributions can align with distinctions that have long been observed through philological close reading. In this sense, the study contributes to an emerging form of computational philology in which statistical methods function not as replacements for textual scholarship, but as supplementary tools for reorganizing and visualizing textual evidence.

The entropy analysis further clarifies the nature of the stylistic differences observed in the PCA results. Although Xuanzang's translation exhibited slightly higher mean entropy values, the differences were not statistically significant. This finding is important because it suggests that the PCA separation is not simply reducible to large-scale differences in lexical richness or textual complexity. Instead, the stylistic distinctions identified by PCA appear to reflect more localized patterns of character distribution and discourse organization within otherwise comparable textual systems.

At the same time, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the corpus examined here is relatively small and limited to a single Buddhist scripture. This limitation partly reflects the intentionally controlled nature of the corpus design: by restricting the analysis to parallel translations of the same scripture, the study minimizes topical variation while necessarily limiting the number of available texts. Second, the study analyzes character-frequency distributions rather than syntactic or semantic structure in a deeper linguistic sense. Third, PCA is ultimately an exploratory rather than deterministic method; the interpretation of principal component loadings necessarily involves philological judgment in addition to statistical observation. A further methodological limitation concerns the use of overlapping textual segments. The overlapping design was adopted primarily to stabilize local frequency distributions within long and weakly punctuated classical Chinese passages, and to generate enough observational units given the limited corpus size. However, because consecutive segments share 50% of their character content, adjacent observations are not fully statistically independent, and this structural correlation should be considered when interpreting the results. Non-overlapping segmentation would avoid this issue, but at the cost of introducing different sources of instability in small-scale classical Chinese corpora, including arbitrary boundary effects and reduced observational units. Future research might systematically compare both segmentation strategies in order to assess the robustness of the patterns reported here. Beyond methodological refinements, future research could also expand the corpus to include additional translators, additional scriptures, or alternative stylometric features such as collocations, n-grams, or semantic embeddings.

Despite these limitations, the study suggests that interpretable stylometric methods can contribute meaningfully to Buddhist translation studies. The results suggest that quantitative

analysis can generate philologically readable evidence concerning stylistic organization in this pair of parallel Buddhist translations.

5 Conclusion

This study applied character-frequency stylometry and principal component analysis to a comparison of the Kumārajīva and Xuanzang translations of the *Diamond Sutra*. By analyzing fixed-length textual segments drawn from parallel translations of the same scripture, the study identified interpretable stylistic distinctions despite the shared doctrinal framework of the two texts.

In this corpus, Kumārajīva's segments are associated with more formulaic dialogue markers, while Xuanzang's segments are associated with more connective and expository forms, alongside more technical Buddhist terminology. Within this corpus, the latter also appears to preserve more transliterated Indic expressions. These findings broadly correspond to long-standing philological observations within Buddhist translation studies while providing quantitative evidence for those distinctions.

Methodologically, the study shows that character-frequency PCA can function as an interpretable exploratory tool within computational philology. Rather than treating stylometry solely as a classification technique, the study emphasizes the interpretive value of principal component loadings and their relationship to historically meaningful textual features.

More broadly, the study suggests that digital humanities methods can contribute productively to Buddhist textual scholarship when statistical analysis and philological interpretation are treated as complementary rather than opposing approaches. Even relatively simple quantitative methods may reveal stylistic structures in small, controlled corpora that are difficult to observe through close reading alone while remaining interpretable for humanistic analysis.

Future research might extend this framework to additional translation pairs, including scriptures transmitted across Esoteric Buddhist traditions, where the tension between terminological precision and liturgical accessibility introduces yet another dimension of translational choice. Expanding the corpus in this direction would allow the interpretable stylometric approach developed here to be tested against a wider range of historical translation contexts within the Chinese Buddhist canon.

Data and Code Availability

An anonymized replication package containing the source texts, analysis notebook, PCA outputs, loading tables, entropy statistics, and generated figures is publicly available at: <https://github.com/anonymoussdhresearch-coder/diamond-sutra-stylometry>

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